

Impact of Communication of a Leader: A Case Study of Indian Leader (Mr. Suresh Prabhu, Minister of Commerce, Industry & Aviation)

Syed Umer Ahmad Qadri¹, Suhail Mohammad Ansari²

¹Ph.D, Department of Linguistics, Lamm Aligarh Muslim University, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Ph.D, Department of Commerce Aligarh Muslim University, Uttar Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

In this research paper, we find how leadership is affected by communication. What all are the key points leader have to keep in mind while communicating with their teams and suggestions. Good communication skills are considered to be the most imperative skills a leader must have. For an effective leader it is obligatory to ensure persuasion, responsibility, premeditated association, creating and managing value system and to provide support and motivation to his teams. A leader is capable to accomplish all this by effective leading, sound planning, monitoring and communicating. Among these mention factors perfect and precise communication is of utmost importance. It is a leader's communication skills which motivate and inspire teammates to work hard and achieve team targets and organizational goals as well. Effective communication act as an advantage of a leader to lead effectively.

Keywords: *Effective communication, leadership, quality, motivation, control, accountability, extraordinary, individual, organizational, responsibility*

INTRODUCTION

Effective and accurate communications are an imperative factor to develop as a productive and fruitful leader. As per numerous specialists, a leader is one who has a capacity to assume responsibility, coordinate, support, or empower others. They have a state of mind to persuade others and to influence them.

Good relational abilities help to grow better understanding and convictions among individuals

move them to take after the standards and qualities which their leader needs to instill in them. Without great relational abilities, a leader neglects to accomplish the objectives set by him and by the associations and a makes him an ineffective leader. By connecting all the more effectively with his group and associates, an administrator can build his potential and will have the capacity to complete work by colleagues. The great leader is extremely very much aware with the way that beneficial communication isn't a restricted procedure rather there are two key components which finish communication process: talking and tuning in with comprehension.

Leadership is an influence process that enables managers to get their people to do willingly what must be done, do well what ought to be done. (Cribbin, J.J)

They realize that they can't make this procedure proceeds until the point that unless they are heard and seen properly by their colleagues. To make this procedure smooth a successful chief has very much arranged goals in his mind which he has thought to be accomplished subsequent to convey. For accomplishing the targets of the communication, leader envisions the supposition, feelings and learning level of the collector and get ready activity to help correspondence to influence others to comprehend the message needs to convey. He conveys the all around arranged messages with influence and relates them to the point and targets to be accomplished with the assistance of correspondence. Requesting compliance or comprehension of the message in a roundabout way is one of the key note characteristics of a decent leader.

Leadership is interpersonal influence, exercised in a situation, and directed, through the communication process, toward the attainment of a specified goal or goals. (Tannenbaum, Weschler & Massarik)

Asking for confirmation or understanding of the message indirectly is one of the key note qualities of a good leader. While receiving any message, he keeps all his doors open and try to figure out the main idea. Even in case of negative feedback he doesn't lose his heart and take it as an opportunity to learn new things. He always tries to understand the weak points and analyses the usefulness of the communication. In case of miss-communication taking corrective measure to rectify the mistake is also important and must be done by the managers or leaders. Hence, to establish oneself as a great and effective leader one must be an effective convincing communicator and needs to learn skilfully the art of extraordinary communication, this would further support manager and his team to attain new levels of quality leadership. Ethos is also acting as an important aspect of effective leadership. It is must for a leader to be sensitive towards moral ideologies.

Leader communication is characterized as motivating and empowering an individual or a gathering by precise and important sharing of data by utilizing phenomenal relational abilities. Initiate communication is a perplexing procedure which begins with creating a methodology for importing, composing correctly and after that talking adequately to control troublesome circumstances. Authority communication has three noteworthy angles: Core, Managerial, and corporate. With an expansion in leader's portfolio there is a need to extemporize relational abilities to oversee huge skyline also, to end up significantly more compelling every single conceivable circumstance. Leaders can build up a culture of trust and can undoubtedly assemble relationship with representatives and different business channels that encourage associations to develop all the more quickly. Put stock in building exercises incorporates correspondence administration, sourcing the privilege systems, positive discussion about what else to be done and criticism of the communication. Trust is basic since it is the trust of the general population that has the ability to make a tremendous frame slight and change over major into minor. Consequently, it is must for a hierarchical leader to ensure that the general population, related with them contain confidential in factor.

The objectives of the research paper:

The main objectives of this research paper are as follows:

- To explore communication elan of the Indian leader
- To find out the quality of the Indian leader.
- To identify the relationship of the Indian leader with office secretariats and peoples.
- To find out the ability of the Indian leader.
- To identify the impact of the Indian leader on peoples.
- To identify the challenges involved with Indian leader
- To find out the management skills of the Indian leader

DATA ASSORTMENT:

The material studied in this paper was extracted from the internet, social sites, and one thousand two hundred people's opinions from three different states like Maharashtra, Uttar-Pradesh and Delhi, telephonic conversations with his personal assistant and his social media assistant and observations.

Few opinions of scholars about Mr. Suresh Prabhu as;

Akram Azad (PRESIDENT AT AASRA THE FOUNDATION, NGO BAHRAICH) opines that he is a leader with futuristic vision for the country and for his peoples.

Pallav Vishnu, (Guest faculty, AMU); opines that he has the ability to judge people's very fast. This is the unique quality finds in very few leaders.

Danish Rahim (scholar) said that he is very down to earth and has vision for development through his power. He uses his power in development of the country. I saw his development policy on the internet, either as a minister of railway or minister of commerce, industry and civil aviation is excellent.

Irfan Ahmad (PDF in Sanskrit department) opines that he is very honest and hard working leader. He is most responsible leader than others.

Syed Afzal Ali, (Research fellow from Gonda) opines that he is a non controversial figure in spite of that every leader in same party wants consideration through negative politics.

Mohd. Rehan, (Research scholar from Moradabad) opines that he is honest and non controversial leader in Indian politics. He has ability to manage the crucial situation through his knowledge and experience.

Tanveer Ahmad (business man from Mumbai) said that he is a leader with many qualities like speaker, managing ability.

Parvez Ahmad (form Delhi) opines that he has unique governing style in running the ministry by his caliber.

RESEARCH METHOD:

In this research paper the qualitative research methods are used to find out the quality of a leader.

- We planned a communication program through appointment with Mr. Suresh Prabhu in his office.
- The aims of this research paper are to explore the quality of a leader.
- This research paper aims are to gain insights into Mr. Suresh Prabhu's lifestyle, culture, behavior, and preferences.

Tompkins and Cheney's organizational control theory is an extension of Weberian theory applied to organizations that are moving past the bureaucratic mode but are yet to be totally amorphous. This theory holds that there are four kinds of control that determine how organizations exercise power within and they are simple, technical, and bureaucratic. In a way, these four types of control are defined according to the progression of the organization from very simple organizational models to pure bureaucracies to overly technical and finally an organization where everyone knows what is expected of him or her and has the purpose of the organization's mission and vision clearly etched within them. The point here is that Tompkins and Cheney posit a model where control and communication is more than what Weber had envisaged and less than what postmodern theorists say about organizational control and communication.

Leadership elan Influencing Communication;

Mr. Suresh Prabhu is concerned with the practice and use of diverse leadership elan under unlike situations according to the need of audiences and personal leadership qualities. Under every situation the communication gets affected as some situations demand direct and strict communication and in other situation he opts for indirect ways of communication.

Stroke Based Leader

Mr. Suresh Prabhu gives an emphasis to these points; assignment, group and individual. He concentrates on the assignment given, the team working on that assignment and individual issues of the team members and should try to meet the deadlines by focusing on each one at different times. Here, the main drive of the team is to get the work done and he upholds the focus of the team to achieve objectives

Aim Orientated Leader;

Mr. Suresh Prabhu has a vision or goal for him and for his team. This vision or goals are synchronized with organizational aims and objectives. He communicates the vision and goals for his team so as to motivate them to achieve them with efficiency. He communicates in a way so that he will be able to make others see what he is expecting from them. Team involvement, effective listening, clear and timely communication is the main feature of his style.

Directional Leadership Elan:

Mr. Suresh Prabhu helps his teams to achieve their personal work targets and team targets by telling them the appropriate methods and showing the right directions to achieve those goals. He acts as a director, who support and enables his team to follow the path which leads them to achieve their goals more easily and perfectly by communicating effectively.

Leadership Elan According to the Intellectual Level:

Mr. Suresh Prabhu adjusts his leadership elan by keeping in mind the intellectual level and maturity of the employees. Here maturity does not refer to the sensitivity or age, but it means work stability, tendency to handle complex situations, potential of achieving given target. Effective leaders always try to maintain a good balance by adjusting the leadership method which further has an influence on communication.

Behavioral Leadership Elan:

Mr. Suresh Prabhu distinguishes his leadership in two ways; one is a work-orientated and the other one is individual orientated. Accomplishment, inspiration, readiness and aptitude to take accountability, the leanings and knowledge regulate the blend of his style. This leadership elan does not depend on so many ways, but it hinges on the situation, where and why it has to be used. The consequence of this style is that during communication, associations must have

sufficient consideration to make the interaction a successful one.

Analysis of questions and answer session hours in parliament:

Context	Venue	Purpose	Remark
Mr. Suresh Prabhu Question & Answer session.	Parliament	Information; He provides the information related to his work done in railway development .	The peoples of the country as well the leader who asked questions to Mr. Suresh Prabhu satisfied.

The above analysis shows the quality of Mr. Suresh Prabhu. He has a capacity to assume responsibility, coordinate, support, or empower others. They have a state of mind to persuade others and to influence them. He has mastered at controlling hard to troublesome conditions.

FINDINGS:

- Mr. Suresh Prabhu is best communicator.
- He is icon of intelligence and wisdom.
- He knows very well how to deal in crucial situations.
- He has administrative skills.
- He has a future vision for the work which is related to him or his ministry.
- His relational abilities help him to grow better understanding and conviction among individuals and groups.
- He is very much concerned with the practice and use of diverse leadership elan.
- He has a great quality to connecting all the more effectively with his group, associates, and individuals.
- He has the competences to motivate team to achieve which seems to be impossible for others.
- His communication skills make him effective who develops better understanding in teams.
- He has the ability to build up a culture of trust and can undoubtedly assemble relationship with representatives and different business channels that encourage associations to develop all the more quickly.
- When he receives any message, he keeps all his doors open and try to figure out the main idea.

CONCLUSION:

In this research analysis, we find these qualities should be in leader. A leader cannot become an effective leader until unless he is an excellent communicator and must use his ability to let individuals follows him. He must have knowledge and will be able to communicate that knowledge to others at work. A leader must have the competences to motivate team to achieve which seems to be impossible for others. Communication makes a leader effective who develops better understanding in teams. These understanding bring a sense of trust in employees on the leader and on each other, work together, which further reinforce congenial relations with team members and creates an excellent work atmosphere. While working with such a good, healthy, positive and congenial environment they get motivated and enthusiastic to work much harder. In some of the style like where the leader has to handle a tough or critical situation he need to be little hard and leadership elan will become authoritative, but must have a control on his communication otherwise it may become a miss-communication or an ineffective one. In another example where has to deal with a group with different work attitude and elan, here he needs to be more people centric and should communicate in a way that he will be able to communicate at individual levels even while interacting with a group.

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